

**Inclusion of Social welfare Education into Adult Education Programme Reforms and
National Integration in Nigeria**

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Abstract

One of the virgin speciality in the field of adult education as an academic discipline is Social Welfare Education. Contemporarily, the practice of social welfare cannot be undertaken effectively without rigorous educational training towards professionalism among social welfare officers and workers. Hence, many schools of social welfare education have been established in Great Britain, America, Asia, Scandinavian and some countries in Africa. The goals were to provide adequate staffing for social welfare programme at various levels of endavours. This paper discussed the concepts of social welfare and education; development of welfare state from global perspective narrowing down to Nigeria, and described the need for inclusion of social welfare education into adult education programme reform and national integration in Nigeria. The paper concluded that Adult educational reform is the key to participation in the global insurgent communities of the 21st century, which Nigeria is not in exception. This was based on increasing level of people needing relief intervention, community restructuring, and disaster management skills. The recommendation made by the paper is that; there is the need for the NBTE and NUC to negotiate for a reform in the adult education programme for harmonization of social development, social work, and community development into one single curriculum that will facilitate continous academic programme up to the PhDs in social welfare speciality, and Government, NGOs, and other practitioners of social welfare should be given adequate chances and sponsorship for their staff to undergo the available social welfare academic trainings. This will enhance career choice and development amongst them.

Key words: Adult education, Reforms, Social welfare education, Social work, and Welfare state.

Introduction

A part from adult and non-formal education, distance education, extension education, to mention a few, one of the virgin specialities in the field of adult education as an academic discipline is social welfare education. Social welfare is the organised system of social services and institutions designed to aid individuals and groups to attain satisfying standards of life and health, and personal and social relationships that permit them to develop their full capacities and to promote their well-being in harmony with the needs of their families and communities (Crompton, 1980 cited in Atolagbe, 1990). With diversification of social activities such as religious and cultural beliefs; geographical conditions and other forms of economic activities, individuals, communities and states in Nigeria have needs, goals and aspirations to be enhanced. This can only be facilitated through programmes that improved betterment and well-being of the general public in terms of reforms for national integration as specified in the national philosophy of education. Thus, according to Molagun, (1999), “education is the process through which the cultural values of a people, knowledge, understanding skills and abilities are transmitted among its populace in order to prepare them for further membership and participation in the maintenance, growth and development of the society”. Reforms in adult education programme therefore may likely facilitate social welfare education as an academic discipline towards national integration in Nigeria. This paper therefore attempts to discuss the development of welfare state from global perspective narrowing down to Nigeria, describe the need for inclusion of social welfare education into adult education programme in the academic field, and offer recommendation for reforms targeted on national integration in Nigeria.

Social Welfare Education

However, social welfare education as viewed by Tamburro, (2013) is the academic field which involves series of curricula activities meant for providing knowledge, skills and values that support and enhance the ability of individuals who worked in the field of social welfare speciality.

For the purpose of development of specialities in the field of adult education practice, social welfare education emerged to provide education programmes that are targeted in the provision of well trained and adequate personnel that would cover the aspects of professionalism in the field of social welfare. Such that courses ranging from diploma, higher diploma, and degrees would be automatically run to provide highly trained and professionalized manpower that will work at various public, private, and non-governmental organizations in the States.

In the past two centuries, becoming welfare state have been the concern of governments through development of policies and reforms commonly found in Europe and American states. Welfare State however, according to the encyclopedia Britannica is,

“a concept of government in which the state plays a key role in the protection and promotion of the economic and social well-being of its citizens. It is based on the principles of equality of opportunity, equitable distribution of wealth, and public responsibility for those unable to avail themselves of the minimal provisions for a good life.

The general term may cover a variety of forms of economic and social organization.” (p.1)

Some of countries in Europe, Asia, America, and the Scandinavian (Sweden, Norway, Finland, and Denmark) are the modern welfare states which employ a system known as the Nordic model. The welfare state involves a direct transfer of funds from the states budgetary allocations to the services provided such as education, healthcare, housing, transportation, and rehabilitation as well as relief directly to individuals who have experienced various forms of disaster. In addition to this however, oil producing countries embraced welfare state such as Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirate, Brunei, Kuwait, Qatar, Bahrain and Oman all became welfare state for their citizens but not for foreign nationals legally resident or employed. According to Esping-Andersen (1990) there are three ways of organizing a welfare state. While in the first model Rothstein, (1998) argues that the state is primarily concerned with the directing the resources to the people most in need; this requires a tight bureaucratic control over the people concerned. The second model; the state distributes welfare with as little bureaucratic interference as possible, to all people who fulfill easily established criteria (for example; having children, receiving medical treatment), this requires high taxation. This model was constructed by the Scandinavian ministers Karl Kreistian Steeincke and Gustav Moller in the 30s and is dominant in Scandinavian. And the third model is similar to the one practiced in Britain (Beveridge model) and is based more on citizenship and a certain level of welfare as a right, which may then be modified according to needs.

Based on comparative histories of actual welfare state, Esping-Andersen, (1990) argued that they fall in to three types of policies: liberalist (heavily means tested, limited services), corporatist (pre-market conservative welfare state in origin, social insurance schemes), and social democratic (universalistic “Beveridge” style social rights based on citizenship instead of working life). The main question now is that “is Nigeria a welfare state”.

The modern welfare programmes differ from previous schemes of poverty relief due to their relatively universal coverage. Apart from old age pensions, or unemployment benefits, and in-kind welfare services such as health or childcare services, welfare system had been developing globally intensively since the end of the World War II. At the end of the century due to their restructuring, part of their responsibilities stated to be channeled through non-governmental organizations which became important providers of social services.

In Nigeria, the national social development policy was adopted in October, 1989. The fundamental social objective on which the policy document takes it root is the protection and advancement of the rights, security, dignity and welfare of the people (Anyanwu, 1991). It was also stated in the document that social development agencies recognized in Nigeria are government (Federal, State and Local); local community; private sector agencies (business sector, voluntary non-profit organizations); international agencies, and mass media. The main concern of the government in Nigeria at all the levels was the attainment of welfare state. This was the result of the government effort to recognize and allocate expenditure in its annual budgetary allocations across the tiers. Contemporarily, in 20th century emerged the social protection system which also covers aspects of well-being of the citizenry. Various institutions and several programmes were established with the objectives of protection of the rights as well as provision of effective services that overlook the general well-being of the citizens at various levels of endeavours. This makes us believe that Nigeria

is also a welfare state; hence, it provides services such as education, health, relief, money and empowerment programmes targeted on the provision of employment among youth and vulnerable individuals and groups.

Ideally, the global transformation of societies to welfare states was achieved with the effective participation of legislature, professionals, international associations of social welfare, and many other partners such as the ILO. Issues of education, training, and professional associations which regulate the ethical principles of professional conduct are obviously the concern of social welfare education practitioners. In America and Canada each social work curriculum component (policy, research, practice, ethics, human behaviour/human development) incorporate indigenous perspectives, and content. This inclusion of indigenous histories and voices into a post-colonial discourse of social work education help to decolonize social work practice and provide a fundamental context for the transformation of Western social work educational systems. A historical context was then provided that helped students understand the multi-generational trauma of indigenous peoples. This understanding was a key to develop positive solutions to many of the issues facing indigenous peoples (Duran, Duran and Yellow Horse Brave Heart, 1998). A school or department of social work within a university is bound to adhere to the basic principles of intellectual inquiry, including respect for evidence, open-mindedness about debatable questions, and intellectual autonomy for students and scholars. Some of the pioneer universities offering social work education include Arizona State University, Universities of California at Berkeley and Los Angeles, University of Central Florida, University of Central Houston, University of Washington, and Wayne State University. Others from the UK include the Oxford University, University of Leeds, Stirling University, Queens University Belfast, Glasgow Caledonian University, to mention a few.

In Nigeria, schools that offer social development, social administration, and social work courses at polytechnics were found suitable for training social workers who are found in the lowest tier for auxiliary workers, the *aides sociales*, rural *animateurs* or community development village level workers. These are usually involved in the policy planning/implementation and administration of social welfare services as well as provision of relevant social services at the various tiers of government. Contemporarily, some universities in Nigeria have incorporated social welfare/work into their curricula. While some universities run the programmes in the faculties of arts and social science, others run the programmes in the faculties of education and humanities. For those universities running the programmes in the faculties of education such as the department of adult education and community services, it becomes necessary for the schools to facilitate research and development in the curricular. Since the polytechnics have been awarding certificates, diplomas (lower and higher) the universities have provided avenue for continuity in pursuance of first degree, masters, and PhDs in the field of social welfare speciality.

Adult Education Programme Reforms and National Integration in Nigeria

For the purpose of writing a comprehensive literature for this paper, it is of great importance to discuss the state of educational reform in Nigeria. Despite there are many controversies in the educational sector, and hence the reforms in the adult education sector in the Nigerian higher institutions need to be reformed adequately. Education as opined by Mkpa (1987), is supposed to be a problem-solving instrument for the learner and the society. Since society's problems change

so must educational system. National Policy on Education - NPE (2004) asserts that education fosters the worth and development of the individual, for each individual's sake, and for the general development of the society. There is need for functional education for the promotion of a progressive, united Nigeria, to this end, school programmes need to be relevant, practical and comprehensive, while interest and ability should determine the individual's direction in education. Nigeria's philosophy of education is based on:

- i. The development of the individual into a sound and effective citizen;
- ii. The full integration of the individual into the community and,
- iii. The provision of equal access to educational opportunities for all citizens of the country at the primary, secondary and tertiary levels both inside and outside the formal school system.

For the philosophy to be in harmony with Nigeria's national goals, education has to be geared towards self-realization, better human relationship, individual and national efficiency, effective citizenship, national consciousness, national unity, as well as towards social, cultural, economic, political, scientific and technological progress. Therefore, the quality of instruction at all levels has to be oriented towards inculcating respect for the worth and dignity of the individual, faith in man's ability to make rational decisions; shared responsibility for the common good of society; acquisition of competencies necessary for self-reliance (NPE, 2004). In order to achieve or realize the above statements for the learner and society through education, reform is the way out. It is justified that having majority of the population in Nigeria are vulnerable to various social and economic problems. Emphasis should be made to address the current need for social welfare educators that will be engaged in the teaching and learning programmes in the higher institutions of learning in Nigeria. The reforms in the adult education programmes agenda facilitate the development of curricular activities that covers all the programmes designed for production of knowledgeable personnel that will be involved in the planning, organization, and management of social welfare institutions in Nigeria. For the national integration, reforms in the adult education programmes of activities such as development of learning programmes in social work and social welfare need to be the academic programmes that whenever integrated in the Universities in Nigeria will automatically ensure adequate participation of learners who have the interest in the development of the well-being of the citizenry.

Conclusions

Adult educational reform is the key to participation in the global insurgent communities of the 21st century, which Nigeria is not in exception. This was based on increasing level of people needing relief intervention, community restructuring, and disaster management skills. Education as Achuonye and Ajoku (2003) in Achuonye (2007) put it functions as an agent for the maintenance of social status quo in the society through the transmission of modern ideas, modern strategies of doing things. In an effort to better meet the diverse needs of learners and ultimately of the society, there have been numerous curricular reforms and the introduction of a range of new approaches and strategies in the class room environment. This is where the reform in the adult education programmes can benefit every youth and adult the educational opportunities designed to meet their basic learning and personal needs such as literacy, numeracy, oral expression and problem solving) and the basic learning content (such as knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes in the of social

welfare speciality) required by human beings to be able to survive, to develop their full capacities, to live and work in dignity, to participate fully in development to improve the quality of their lives and to make informed decisions. These issues are obviously the major concerns of social welfare and social work as professional fields of specialisation. The basic learning needs of youths and adults are diverse and should be met through a variety of educational reform programmes. These programmes can include women education and empowerment, youth development, family case work, community development, rehabilitation programmes and services, child protection, and many others.

Husain (2004) went further to say that the learner and society need educational reform because it helps to build human potentials, builds upon responsibility, active participation, reflection and flexibility which creates competences that develop active citizens and further democratic behaviour. If these can be integrated in Nigeria, it will give quality learning that enables the learners to function in various roles as individuals as well as part of the work force which takes place in the school and outside. It is a driving force that helps individuals and society to move from the practice of educational mono culture to a system which recognizes that human beings have a wide range of variety of socially useful talents, all of which should be developed through educational reforms. Useful talents like those meant to pursue “brother own keeper” which signifies the worth personality in each individual is the main philosophy of social welfare.

Recommendations

This paper therefore recommends that:

- i. There is the need for the National Board of Technical Education (NBTE) and Nigeria Universities Commission (NUC) to negotiate for a reform in the adult education programme for harmonization of social development, social work, and community development into one single curriculum that will facilitate continues academic programme up to the PhDs in social welfare speciality., and
- ii. Government, NGOs, and other practitioners of social welfare should be given adequate chances and sponsorship for their staff to undergo the available social welfare academic trainings. This will enhance career choice and development amongst them.

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